

Design of Rectangular Microstrip Patch Antenna

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Abstract

Communication system have been said to have a rapid growth and has been attracting interest for the last few years. Today in the world of communication systems the most widely researched area is of wireless technology and a study of communication systems is incomplete without an understanding of the operation of the antennas. In the recent years of development in communication systems a need for the development of lightweight, compact and cost-effective antennas that are capable of maintaining high performance over a wide spectrum of frequencies. This technological trend has focused much effort into the design of a Micro strip patch antenna. In this work a rectangular microstrip patch antenna is theoretically designed. The important parameters of the microstrip patch antenna like bandwidth, efficiency, are analysed for five different substrate materials. Hence the antenna efficiency, band width, impedance etc., with the related parameters are tuned. My aim of this framework that sets institutional standards and defines commitments on gender equality and the empowerment of women through my small contribution in the communication field on Microstrip patch Antenna for the welfare of the humanity.

Introduction

The communication field is concerned with television, radio, newspapers, magazines, advertisements, computers, internet and so forth. [1] The main purpose of this research paper is to focus upon the role & contribution of women in communication; how women have contributed towards the development of communication within the country & the world. Women are attaining higher educational qualifications and are assuming different professional roles such as scientists, doctors, teachers, lawyers, administrators, managers, entrepreneurs and so forth. Women have rendered and are rendering a very significant contribution towards the development of communication. They are employed and playing the lead role in the communication field as scientist. The main areas that have been highlighted in this research paper are, portrayal of women in science which is in the main field of communication.

Hedy Larmarr was a Hollywood star who spent her insights developing a frequency-hopping communication system.

Vinod krishan is a Indian physicist, is a Senior Professor and Dean of Sciences at the Indian Institute of Astrophysics, Bangalore. She is involved in teaching and research in Plasma Physics. She is a Fellow of the National Academy of Sciences, India and a recipient of the Vikram Sarabahi Award for Space Sciences.

Bimla Buti is an Indian physicist and specialized in the field of plasma physics. She was the first Indian woman Physicist, Fellow of Indian National Science Academy(INSA). In 1994, she was awarded INSA-Vainu Bappu Award.

As I am being woman, I want to render service for the welfare of the humanity through my research in the field of communication.

An Antenna is a transducer, which converts electrical power into electromagnetic waves and vice versa. An Antenna can be used either as a transmitting antenna or a receiving antenna[3]. A transmitting antenna is one, which converts electrical signals into electromagnetic waves and radiates them. A receiving antenna is one, which converts electromagnetic waves from the received beam into electrical signals. In two-way communication, the same antenna can be used for both transmission and reception. Antenna can also be termed as an Aerial. Plural of it is, antennae or antennas. Now-a days, antennas have undergone many changes, in accordance with their size and shape. Microstrip patch antenna consists of a radiating patch on one side of a dielectric substrate which has ground plane on the other side. The patch is generally made of conducting material such as copper or gold and can take any possible shape. The radiating patch and the feed lines are usually photo etched on the dielectric substrate. In this work the microstrip patch antenna is designed to operate at a frequency of 10 GHz. The optical properties are analyzed using five different dielectric substrates for a substrate height of 1.5mm.

Basic Principles of Operation

The metallic patch essentially creates a resonant cavity, where the patch is the top of the cavity, the ground plane is the bottom of the cavity, and the edges of the patch form the sides of the cavity. The edges of the patch act approximately as an open-circuit boundary condition. Hence, the patch acts approximately as a cavity with perfect electric conductor on the top and bottom surfaces, and a perfect “magnetic conductor” on the sides[4].

This point of view is very useful in analyzing the patch antenna.

Design Specification

The three essential parameters for the design of a rectangular microstrip patch antenna are (i) Frequency of Operation - The resonant frequency of the antenna must be selected appropriately. Dielectric constant of the substrate (ϵ_r). The dielectric substrates Bakelite, FR4 Glass Epoxy, RO4003, Taconic TLC and RT Duroid, which are used for the fabrication of microstrip patch antenna, has been studied. Height of dielectric substrate (h) the transmission line model is used to design the antenna.

Calculation of Effective Dielectric Constant

The dielectric constant is the ratio of the permittivity of a substance to the permittivity of free space. The following equation gives the effective dielectric constant of the microstrip patch antenna as

$$\epsilon_{eff} = \frac{\epsilon_r + 1}{2} + \frac{\epsilon_r - 1}{2} \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + 12 \left(\frac{h}{w} \right)}} \right]$$

ϵ_{eff} = Effective dielectric constant ϵ_r = Dielectric constant of substrate

h = Height of dielectric substrate

W = Width of the patch ; L = Length of the Antenna

The typical impedance at the edge of a resonant rectangular patch can be approximated as

Input Impedance

$$z_{in} = 90 \frac{\epsilon_r^2}{\epsilon_r - 1} \left(\frac{L}{W} \right)^2$$

Calculation of the Length Extension (ΔL)

The dimensions of the patch along its length have been extended on each end by a distance ΔL, which is a function of the effective dielectric constant and the width-to-height ratio. A very popular and practical approximation relation for the normalized extension of the length

$$\text{Length extension} = \frac{c}{2 f_0 \sqrt{\epsilon_{eff}}} - 0.824 \left(\frac{(\epsilon_{eff} + 0.3) \left(\frac{W}{h} + 0.264 \right)}{(\epsilon_{eff} - 0.258) \left(\frac{W}{h} + 0.8 \right)} \right)$$

Using the above equation, the values of length extension for various substrate mediums may be calculated. Because of using five different dielectric substrate, so height of dielectric substrate is 1.5 mm. Using the above equation, we get the length extension the different substrate.

Table 1 Calculated Optical Parameters of Various Substrate Antennas

S. No.	Substrate	Dielectric Constant	Resonant frequency GHz	Height (mm)	Width (mm)	Length (mm)
1	RT Duroid	2.2	10	1.5	11.85	9.122
2	R04003	3.2	10	1.5	10.34	7.609
3	Taconic	3.4	10	1.5	10.11	7.3484
4	Fr4	4.36	10	1.5	9.15	6.513
5	Bakelite	4.78	10	1.5	8.817	6.212

Calculation of Band Width (W)

In general band width is proportional to the volume, which for a rectangular microstrip antenna at a constant resonant frequency can be expressed as

$$B W \approx \frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon_r}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon_r}} \sqrt{\epsilon_r} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon_r}}$$

Therefore the bandwidth is inversely proportional to the square root of the dielectric constant of the substrate.

Here the width of the microstrip patch antenna is given by equation

The bandwidth for a microstrip antenna as a function of the normalized height of the substrate, for five different substrates are calculated using the above expression and is given in Table.

Table 2 Variation of Bandwidth With the Substrate Height of the Dielectrics

S.No.	Resonance Frequency (GHz)	Substrate Dielectric Constant	Variation Substrate of height (mm)	Width (mm)	Length (mm)	Bandwidth
1	10	2.2	1	11.85	9.500	11.2575
			1.5	11.85	9.122	16.21
			2	11.85	8.730	20.69
			2.5	11.85	8.334	24.689
			3	11.85	7.940	28.22
			3.5	11.85	7.549	31.309
2		3.2	1	10.34	7.928	8.197552
			1.5	10.34	7.609	11.801559
			2	10.34	7.274	15.042632
			2.5	10.34	6.932	17.91922
			3	10.34	6.591	20.44282
			3.5	10.34	6.252	22.625988
3		3.4	1	10.11	7.696	7.780656
			1.5	10.11	7.384	11.197836
			2	10.11	7.055	14.26521
			2.5	10.11	6.720	16.9848
			3	10.11	6.386	19.368738
			3.5	10.11	6.053	21.4185
4		4.36	1	9.156	6.802	6.2
			1.5	9.156	6.513	8.9
			2	9.156	6.20	11.36
			2.5	9.156	5.896	13.49
			3	9.156	5.584	15.33

Calculation of Antenna Efficiency

Psp =The power radiated in space waves

Psu =The power radiated on surface waves

Psp+ Psu is then the total power delivered to the printed

$$P_{sp} = \frac{1}{\lambda_0^2} * (Koh)^2 * (80\pi^2 \mu c l) \text{ Here } cl = 1 - \frac{1}{n^2} + \frac{2}{n^4}$$

Where, cl is constant that depends upon the substrate of material & n is the index refraction of the substrate

$$n = \sqrt{\epsilon_r \mu_r}$$

$$P_{sp} = 80 \left(1 - \frac{1}{\mu_r \epsilon_r} + \frac{2}{\mu_r^2 \epsilon_r^2} \right)$$

$$P_{sw} = \frac{1}{\lambda^2} (k_0 h)^2 * \left[(60 \pi^2 \mu_r^2 \left(1 - \frac{1}{\mu_r^2} \right)^2) \right]$$

Hence efficiency is

$$E = \frac{\frac{1}{\lambda^2} (k_0 h)^2 * [80 \pi^2 \mu_r c l]}{\frac{\mu_r^2}{\lambda^2} (k_0 h)^2 [80 \pi^2 c l + 60 \pi^2 \mu_r \left(1 - \frac{1}{\mu_r^2} \right)^2] * (k_0 h)}$$

substituting cl we get,

$$E = \frac{80 \left(1 - \frac{1}{\mu_r \epsilon_r} + \frac{2}{\mu_r^2 \epsilon_r^2} \right)}{80 \left(1 - \frac{1}{\mu_r \epsilon_r} + \frac{2}{\mu_r^2 \epsilon_r^2} \right) + 60 \pi \sqrt{\mu_r \epsilon_r} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\mu_r \epsilon_r} \right)^2 * (K_0 h)}$$

Hence the antenna efficiency is calculated for various substrate materials.

Results & Discussions

By keeping the resonance frequency at 10 GHz and the height as 1.5 mm the length and width for various substrate materials are calculated and is given in Table-1. It shows that when the dielectric constant increases, both the length and the width of the substrate materials are found to be decreased for providing a fixed resonance frequency. Table -2 provide the information about the variation of bandwidth with the substrate height of various dielectrics. Fig 1 shows that efficiency of the antenna decreases as increasing dielectric constant of the substrate material. The typical input impedance at the edge of a resonant rectangular patch is calculated for having different dielectric material and is plotted in Fig 2, It is observed that the input impedance increases with dielectric constant of the materials. Fig 3 shows the variation of bandwidth with respect to substrate heights for different substrate material. It is found that the bandwidth increases with substrate height and also is function of dielectric constant. Band width increases for the substrate having low dielectric constant. We come to know that we can get good efficiency if low dielectric constant material is used as substrate.

Figure 1 Antenna efficiency for various dielectric materials

Figure 2 Input impedance for various substrate materials

Figure 3 Analysis of Bandwidth With Different Substrate Height

Conclusion

Communication system have been said to have a rapid growth and has been attracting interest for the last few years. Small size, light weight, ease of installation are regarded as advantages in relation to the construction of a low profile microstrip antenna. In this work the essential parameters for the design of a rectangular microstrip patch antenna are analyzed in detail. Hence the antenna efficiency, band width, impedance etc., with the related parameters are tuned. This type of tuning of the parameters in micro strip patch antenna gives a lot of advantages which are useful in education, medical, industrial, and scientific field especially in the communication.

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